

PROCESS-INDUCED FAILURE OF DELTOID IN COMPOSITE T-JOINT: FIBER-OPTIC BASED MONITORING AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

One of the difficulties in composite structural application is joining components. T-joint is one of the important elements in aircraft structures that transfers load between vertical and horizontal panels. T-joint is composed of two L-shaped parts, a skin laminate, and a deltoid. In T-joint, it is reported that cracks occur in the deltoid during manufacturing because of the process-induced cure and thermal stress. Even though a number of failure criteria for T-joint have been proposed, they are for mechanical loading and their applicability to prediction of the process-induced failure is questionable. So, there is an urgent need to understand the internal stress-strain change of the deltoid during manufacturing and to clarify the mechanism of this process-induced failure. In this current study, the effect of process-induced failure on tensile strength is investigated at first. Then, strain development in the deltoid during curing is measured using optical fiber sensors embedded in novel ways. A cooling test with liquid nitrogen is also conducted to introduce the deltoid failure. The optical fiber sensors successfully measured internal strain of the deltoid during curing and cooling. The results of the internal strain measurement and numerical simulation showed some important findings about the residual stress development and failure of the deltoid.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is widely used as a structural material in aircraft due to various advantages such as low density and high strength. One of the difficulties in composite structural application is joining components. T-joint is one of the important elements in aircraft structures that transfers load between vertical and horizontal panels. T-joint is composed of two L-shaped parts, a skin laminate, and a deltoid (Fig. 1). In T-joint, it is reported that cracks occur in the deltoid during manufacturing because of the process-induced cure and thermal stress [1]. Many previous researches conducted fracture analysis of T-joint, and various failure indices such as transverse maximum principal stress and LaRC05 have been applied [2, 3]. However, all of these failure indices are for mechanical loading, and their applicability to prediction of the process-induced failure is questionable. Figure 2 compares the analysis results of the transverse maximum principal stress by finite element analysis (FEA) and the micrograph of the actual process-induced crack obtained in the experiment. The stress concentration area in the FEA is different from the actual failure point. This suggests that the mechanism of the process-induced failure is different from the mechanism of failure by mechanical loading. Therefore, there is an urgent need to understand the internal stress-strain change of the deltoid during manufacturing and to clarify the mechanism of this process-induced failure.

In this current study, the effect of the process-induced failure on tensile strength is investigated at first. Then, strain development in the deltoid during curing is measured using optical fiber sensors embedded in novel ways. A cooling test with liquid nitrogen is also conducted to introduce the deltoid failure and discuss the stress change at the time of the failure.

Figure 1: Schematic of specimen.

Figure 2: (a) FEA result of process-induced failure prediction in deltoid.
 (b) Micrograph of actual failure.

2 INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF PROCESS-INDUCED FAILURE ON TENSILE STRENGTH

2.1 Materials and method

Tensile tests were conducted to investigate the effect of process-induced failure on tensile strength. The schematic of the specimens is shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were manufactured from the unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg sheets with interlaminar toughened layer (T800S/3900-2B, Toray Industries, Inc.). The stacking sequence of the L-shaped parts and skin laminate were $[0_2/90_2]_{2s}$ (3.2 mm thickness). The deltoid was filled with the same unidirectional prepreg sheets in the 90° direction. After laminating each part, all parts were assembled, covered with vacuum-bagging film, and cured in the autoclave (Fig. 3). The specimen was cured at 180°C under a pressure of 0.6 MPa. Four specimens with 20 mm width were cut out from the cured specimen. Two of them were further cooled down with liquid nitrogen to introduce the process-induced failure. The schematic of the tensile test is shown in Fig. 4. The stiffener was clamped and pulled up at a rate of 1.0 mm per minute.

Figure 3: (a) Assembly of all parts. (b) Specimen with vacuum-bagging.

Figure 4: Schematic of tensile test.

2.2 Results

Figure 5 shows the failure of the specimens under tensile loading. In the specimens without process-induced failure, an initial crack occurred vertically in the deltoid. Then, the crack propagated along the deltoid/L-shaped-part interface and the deltoid/skin interface. In the specimens with the process-induced failure, in contrast, an initial diagonal crack was present in the deltoid by the thermal loading. When a tensile load was applied, the crack propagated in the two direction as in the specimens without process-induced failure. Figure 6 shows the measured load-displacement curves. In the specimens with the process-induced failure, the stiffness and strength were significantly reduced compared to the specimens without the process-induced failure. This result clearly indicates that it is important to clarify the mechanism of process-induced failure and to suppress the failure.

Figure 5: Failure under tensile load.
(a) Without process-induced crack. (b) With process-induced crack.

Figure 6: Comparison of load-displacement curves in tensile test.

3 STRAIN MEASUREMENT IN DELTOID USING OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS

3.1 Fiber Bragg grating sensor

Optical fiber sensors are widely used for strain measurement of composites due to various advantages such as small diameter (less than 150 μm) and immunity to electromagnetic interference. There are many types of optical fiber sensors, and a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor is used in this current study. The FBG sensor has a structure in which the refractive index is periodically changed in a part of the optical fiber core. When broadband light enters the sensor, interference occurs at this part, and only a narrow spectrum with a specific wavelength (Bragg wavelength) is reflected (Fig. 7). The Bragg wavelength changes linearly with respect to the axial strain change $\Delta\varepsilon$ and the temperature change ΔT . The amount of change is expressed by the following equation [4].

$$\Delta\lambda = C_\varepsilon \Delta\varepsilon + C_T \Delta T \quad (1)$$

C_ε and C_T are the constants of proportionality. In this current study, the strain change is calculated from the Bragg wavelength by compensating the temperature effect using a thermocouple embedded near the FBG sensor.

Figure 7: Schematic of structure and principle of FBG sensor.

3.2 Materials and method

Strain measurements in deltoid were conducted with FBG sensors. The schematic of the specimens is shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were manufactured from the same material as the tensile test specimens. In addition to the specimen configuration used in the tensile tests, the configuration with a thick skin laminate ($[0_2/90_2]_{2S3}$, 9.6 mm thickness) was used. As with the thin skin laminate specimen, the stacking sequence of the L-shaped parts were $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$, and the deltoid was filled with the unidirectional prepreg sheets in the 90° direction. FBG sensors were embedded in three ways (Vertical, $45^\circ A$, $45^\circ B$) as shown in Fig. 1. Figure 8 shows how to embed optical fibers into the deltoid. The sensors were embedded in a minimal invasive manner through tiny holes machined in the aluminum tool, the deltoid and the skin before curing. The hole in the specimen was made by pressing a thin needle (diameter 0.5 mm) into the stacked prepreg sheets using an ultrasonic horn and a jig dedicated for adjusting the pressing depth. The hole was sealed after optical fiber embedment to prevent resin and vacuum leakage. By using this method, strain in arbitrary direction of the deltoid could be measured. Each sensor was embedded at intervals of 20 mm in the longitudinal direction to prevent mutual mechanical interference of the sensors. In addition, thermocouples for temperature compensation were embedded at the interface between L-shaped part and skin laminate near the deltoid. After embedment of the sensors, the specimens were cured at the same conditions with the tensile test specimens. For the reflection spectrum measurement using an optical spectrum analyzer (AQ6317, Ando Electric Co., Ltd), the sampling number, measurement range, and wavelength resolution were set to 1001, 1520-1560 nm, and 0.1 nm respectively. The FBG response and temperature were recorded at 1 min intervals throughout curing.

Cooling tests with liquid nitrogen were then conducted since no cracks occurred during curing. Specimens were gradually cooled so as not to touch the liquid nitrogen directly in order to prevent stress generation by the temperature distribution. The FBG response and temperature were recorded at 1 sec intervals during the cooling tests.

Figure 8: Embedment method of optical fiber into the deltoid.

3.3 Results and discussions

Figure 9 shows the strain development as a function of temperature during curing in each specimen. The zero strain is set to be the gelation point during 180°C holding. In the thin skin laminate specimen, the cure shrinkage strain values at the vertical, 45°A, and 45°B sensors were -5100 $\mu\epsilon$, -2400 $\mu\epsilon$, and -2900 $\mu\epsilon$, and the thermal shrinkage strain changes at the end of the curing were -7400 $\mu\epsilon$, -6100 $\mu\epsilon$, and -7100 $\mu\epsilon$ (Fig. 9(a)). Compared to the strain of the UD plate [5], significantly small strain was measured in the deltoid of T-joint. This suggests that the deformation of the deltoid was restrained by the L-shaped parts and the skin of T-joint. A change in the coefficient of thermal expansion was seen at 130°C during cooling in each specimen. This is considered to be caused by the state change of the thermoplastic particles in the interlaminar toughened layer [5]. In the vertical sensor, the release of strain due to the spring-in deformation of the L-shaped parts was measured during depressurizing at the end of the curing. In the 45° sensors, different amounts of strain were measured for the 45°A and 45°B sensors. This indicates that asymmetric deformation occurred in the deltoid. This asymmetry may be attributed to the initial imperfections due to defects and manufacturing quality variations. In the thick skin laminate specimen, the cure shrinkage strain values in the vertical, 45°A, and 45°B sensors were -6000 $\mu\epsilon$, -3100 $\mu\epsilon$, and -2900 $\mu\epsilon$, and the thermal shrinkage strain changes at the end of the curing were -8100 $\mu\epsilon$, -6700 $\mu\epsilon$, and -7200 $\mu\epsilon$ (Fig. 9(b)). The amount of strain change in the two 45° sensors was almost the same as in the 45°B sensor of the thin skin laminate specimen. In contrast, strain in the vertical sensor increased compared to the thin skin laminate specimen. Unlike in the case of the thin skin laminate specimen, the strain release was not measured at the end of the curing. This is attributed to the high bending stiffness of the skin and the consequent suppression of the spring-in deformation.

Figure 9: Strain development during cure. (a) Thin skin specimen. (b) Thick skin specimen.

Figure 10 shows the results of the strain measurement during cooling tests with liquid nitrogen. In the thin skin laminate specimen, the failure of deltoid occurred at -117°C , and the strain changes in the vertical, 45°A , and 45°B sensors at the failure were $260 \mu\epsilon$, $890 \mu\epsilon$, and $-990 \mu\epsilon$ (Fig. 10(a)). The larger strain change occurred in the 45° sensor compared to the vertical sensor. This result suggests that the residual stress in the 45° direction mainly contributed to the failure. Whereas tensile strain change occurred in the 45°A sensor, compressive strain occurred in the 45°B sensor. This is because the 45°A sensor measured strain in the direction of the crack, and the 45°B sensor measured strain in the direction perpendicular to the crack (Fig. 11). Figure 12 shows the analysis results of stress distribution in the 45° direction before and after crack initiation. The material properties used in the FEA is shown in Table 1 [6, 7]. The crack geometry was determined from the X-ray CT image and the

temperature change measured in the experiment was applied to the model. In the direction perpendicular to the crack, the residual tensile stress was released by the occurrence of the crack. As a result, compressive strain occurred in the 45°B sensor and the tensile strain occurred in the 45°A sensor by the Poisson effect. In the thick skin laminate specimen, in contrast, the crack propagated laterally in the upper part of the deltoid (Fig. 13). As a result, almost no strain change occurred in the 45° sensor, and a large compressive strain change occurred in the vertical sensor by releasing the tensile residual stress (Fig. 10(b), Fig. 14).

(a)

(b)

Figure 10: Strain development during cooling test. (a) Thin skin specimen. (b) Thick skin specimen.

Figure 11: X-ray CT images. (a) 45°A sensor. (b) 45°B sensor.

Figure 12: Comparison of residual stress state σ_{22} in thin skin specimen. (a) Before cracking. (b) After cracking.

Figure 13: Micrographs of failure in deltoid. (a) Thin skin specimen. (b) Thick skin specimen.

Figure 10: Comparison of residual stress state σ_{22} in thick skin specimen. (a) Before cracking. (b) After cracking.

Elastic modulus [GPa]	
E_{11}	134
E_{22}	8.62
E_{33}	8.20
G_{12}	4.68
G_{13}	3.78
G_{23}	2.38
Poisson's ratio	
ν_{12}	0.338
ν_{13}	0.318
ν_{23}	0.571
Thermal expansion coefficient [$\times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$]	
α_1	0.188
α_2	33.5
α_3	44.3

Table 1: Material properties used in the analysis [6, 7].

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effect of process-induced failure on tensile strength was investigated at first. The process induced failure remarkably decreased the residual strength. Then, strain measurements during curing and cooling were performed using FBG sensors embedded in three directions. From the comparison of the strain in the 45° sensors, it was shown that asymmetric deformation occurred in the deltoid probably due to the imperfections of the specimen. It is one of the great advantages of the in-situ measurement technique used in this study that it is possible to acquire the actual strain condition in the deltoid including the initial imperfections. Moreover, it was shown that the failure mode varied depending on the skin thickness and thereby the different strain change was measured by the FBG sensors. By clarifying the correlation between the strain measurement results and the failure modes while changing test parameters, it is possible to propose a new failure index and improve the analysis accuracy. Moreover, there is a possibility that this in-situ measurement technique can be used for quality assurance by estimating the stress state of the deltoid in each product.

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